

Moving from a goods- to a service-oriented organization: A perspective on the role of corporate culture and human resource management

Structured Abstract:

Purpose –This study aims to investigate the internal elements that help in the introduction of a service logic into a goods-oriented organization by focusing on corporate culture and HRM practices.

Design/methodology/approach – The study employs a qualitative single case study research design. Data have been collected through archival data and 14 semi-structured interviews to managers, employees and retailers of a bike manufacturer.

Findings – The research identifies three new internal elements affecting the service orientation of corporate culture of a company with a customization strategy: i) shared vision built up with the participation of the whole organization; ii) rooting the service orientation into the past history; iii) passion and collaborative work deployed through digital tools. Additionally, related to HRM, the research finds another two elements: emotional salary and that a collective way of understanding and sharing the service infusion is needed.

Research limitations – Given that this is a qualitative research based on a single case study the identified key elements of corporate culture and HRM practices cannot be used as a predictive tool. However, the depth of evidence is significant and allows analytical generalizations, which enable us to put forward tentative propositions for future research.

Practical implications – For managers of industrial firms, the identified elements provide an insight on how to smooth the transition from a goods- to a service-oriented organization. The shift demands the development of an adequate corporate culture and a distinctive management of human resources.

Originality/value –Delving deep in previous literature, the research offers to the academic community 5 soft new elements to be studied in the process of service infusion and can guide top managers how to engage the whole organization in a willingly way towards service orientation.

Keywords: customization, servitization, service climate, service infusion, case study.

Paper type: Research paper

1. Introduction

Manufacturing firms are increasingly shifting the focus of their businesses from tangible products to intangible services (Antioco *et al.*, 2008; Fang *et al.*, 2008; Gebauer *et al.*, 2011). Different terms have been employed to define this phenomenon in the management literature, such as transitioning from products to services (Davies, 2004; Oliva and Kallenberg, 2003), servitization of manufacturing (Baines *et al.*, 2009; Neely, 2008; Vandermerwe and Rada, 1988), and service infusion in manufacturing (Brax, 2005; Gustafsson *et al.*, 2010; Kowalkowski *et al.*, 2013; Ostrom *et al.*, 2010). In today's highly competitive markets, one of the ways to gain differentiation from competitors is by offering value-added services (Homburg *et al.*, 2003). For doing so, many organizations from different industries across the world have embraced customization strategies (Ullah and Narain, 2020) to meet customer demands for a unique and tailored offering (Da Silveira *et al.*, 2001; Duray *et al.*, 2000; Neu and Brown, 2005; Homburg *et al.*, 2003; Matthyssens and Vandenbempt, 1998) which implies that manufacturers must build close relationships with customers to obtain knowledge about customer requirements and changes promoting the implementation of successful service strategies (Fliess and Lexutt, 2019; Martinez *et al.*, 2010; Sousa and Da Silveira, 2019; Baines *et al.*, 2020).

This implies that successful service strategies also involve continuous change, adaptability, continuous opportunity adjustment, innovation capture and goal management (Kowalkowski *et al.*, 2013). The analysis of the industrial service research suggests that the successful implementation of a service-oriented strategy requires significant internal and external changes (Homburg *et al.*, 2003; Pereira *et al.*, 2018). Among the factors that should be changed in companies to deliver customized products and more services, on one hand, there are hard factors such as the organizational structure (Kowalkowski, 2011; Neu and Brown, 2005; Pereira *et al.* 2018, Sheth and Sharma, 2008), the organizational distinctiveness (Oliveira *et al.* 2018), distinct business unit (Oliva and Kallenberg, 2003) or resources shared by the product and service business unit (Neu and Brown, 2005). Another hard factor is the proximity of the service to customers that is, the extent to which external customers are aware of a service organization and can easily identify the service contact points (Froehle and Roth, 2004). On the other hand, soft factors refer to characteristics such as culture, values, and employee's behaviors (Bowen *et al.* 1989; Gebauer *et al.*, 2010a, 2010b; Kindström and Kowalkowski, 2014; Pereira *et al.* 2018; Dang *et al.* 2019; Jovanovic *et al.*, 2019) that are needed to successfully implement a service-oriented strategy. Becoming more service-oriented especially requires changes in the firm's corporate culture and human resource management (HRM) (Homburg *et al.*, 2003) but it seems that many firms struggle with these intangible elements (Kindström and Kowalkowski, 2014).

There is not much research on how corporate culture is deployed in organizations with a service logic (Grönroos and Helle, 2010). Some authors have investigated what are the internal elements required for a successful service strategy (Ambroise *et al.*, 2018; Homburg *et al.*, 2003; Pereira *et al.*, 2018) while others have analyzed the impact of different components of service-culture into the firm's performance (Gebauer *et al.*, 2010a and 2010b). But there is a gap in the literature regarding the need for a better understanding of the role of the service orientation of corporate culture and human resource management for successfully introducing a service logic when implementing a customization strategy.

Against this background and with the aim of filling this gap, our research focuses on exploring how two internal factors, service-orientation of corporate culture and service orientation of HRM, are perceived by managers, employees and retailers when moving from a goods- to a service-oriented company (Fliess and Lexutt, 2019; Pereira *et al.*, 2018; Dang *et al.*, 2019; Jovanovic *et al.*, 2019) through a customization strategy (Sousa and Da Silveira 2019) in the case of a bike manufacturer. The study answers the following research questions:

RQ1: How is the service orientation of corporate culture perceived by managers, employees and retailers when implementing a customization strategy?

RQ2: How is the service orientation of human resource management deployed when implementing a customization strategy?

The findings contribute to the literature on industrial services by utilizing the identified corporate cultural elements and HRM practices to understand how manufacturers can move from a goods- to a services-oriented organization, extending the findings of Gebauer *et al.* (2010b) and Pereira *et al.* (2018) with three new internal elements related to the service orientation of corporate culture and two new ones related to HRM practices Gebauer *et al.* (2010b) and answering important questions highlighted by Fliess and Lexut (2019) regarding the role of the team and the reward and compensation system in servitizing companies. Moreover, this study extends the discussion on the role of customization strategies in the implementation of servitization (Martinez *et al.*, 2010; Sousa and Da Silveira, 2019). The findings can add clarity to the process of organizational change and the role of the internal aspects when introducing a service logic into a goods-oriented organization answering a call for more research

on the change process that take places when companies move from a goods- to a service oriented-climate (Baines *et al.*, 2017; Bowen and Schneider, 2014; Ostrom *et al.*, 2010).

This study examines the case of a basque company that is now at a relatively advanced stage of servitization based on a customization strategy. It describes an overview of the company's internal elements and focuses on the service orientation of corporate culture and HRM that facilitates a discussion on the role of these elements for smoothing the move from goods- to a service-oriented organization.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature and develops a research framework. Section 3 justifies and describes the methodology and the measures to be used. In section 4, the main findings of the study are presented, while section 5 goes on to discuss them. Section 6 concludes the paper, describing the study's implication for theory and practice, and outlining its limitations.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. Service orientation of corporate culture

Several scholars acknowledge that the service transition involves a cultural reorientation from a transaction-centered production culture to a relationship-oriented service culture (Vargo and Lusch, 2004; Brax, 2005; Salonen, 2011). The importance of customer orientation (Neu and Brown, 2005), a service orientation (Brax, 2005; Paiola *et al.*, 2012) and their combination (Salonen, 2011) is highlighted (Fliess and Lexutt, 2019).

We understand organizational culture as comprising a number of features, including a shared pattern of basic assumptions which group members have acquired over time as they learn to successfully cope with internal and external organizationally relevant problems (Schein, 2004). Some authors propose static cultural models (Hofstede, 1980; 1991; 2001) and focus on cultural differences mainly in cross-cultural settings, whereas other authors defend a dynamic view of culture (Fang, 2012) to cope with the requirements of the globalized and a more diverse context (Stahl and Tung, 2015; Tung and Stahl, 2018).

While culture is the shared values and beliefs of how things should be and how things are (Ostrom *et al.*, 2010), *organizational climate*, a related concept found in the service literature, can be viewed primarily as the surface layer of culture (e.g., management practices, cultural artifacts, patterns of behavior). In this sense, values, beliefs, and assumptions are a deeper layer of culture.

According to Schneider *et al.* (1998), service climate is employees' shared sense of the service quality-focused policies, practices, and procedures they experience, and the service quality emphasis they observe in behaviors that are rewarded, supported, and expected. Climate is arguably easier to measure and manage than culture and can change more quickly overtime. The necessity to better understand the role of service climate for service infusion in manufacturing was raised by Ostrom *et al.* (2010). The authors focus on the research priorities for service management and highlight the need to identify the cultural changes that would introduce a service logic into goods-oriented organizations and to foster the development of a service mind-set in product-focused ones.

When studying the service climate, some authors state that the key focus is to grasp how manufacturing firms can adopt an overall service logic for the entire business (Grönroos and Halle, 2010), not exclusively for the services it offers. Early conceptual work from this

perspective was offered by Bowen *et al.* (1989), who described a “service-oriented manufacturing configuration”, in which an overall service mindset could emerge thanks to a service-focused strategy, structure, and environment (all three elements being internally consistent, complementary, and mutually reinforcing). They noted that this configuration would include a service-oriented climate that would foster flexibility, relational marketing, and customer co-production which would in turn change the manufacturing firm’s environment (Bowen and Schneider, 2014). In this vein, these authors highlight the utility of the service climate framework when it comes to analyzing service infusion in manufacturing and give several outstanding examples of empirical work on culture and climate issues. One of these studies is conducted by Gebauer *et al.* (2010a), where service orientation is conceptualized and operationalized through service value and behavior at the managerial and employee levels. Furthermore, using the framework by Bowen *et al.* (1989), Gebauer *et al.* (2010b) conclude that for a manufacturing firm trying out a new and different service strategy to succeed, a specific and comprehensive service-focused strategy-structure configuration is necessary regarding the service orientation of corporate culture and the HRM policies.

2.2. Service orientation of human resource management (HRM)

Previous servitization literature has stressed the role of managers and employees as critical for implementing the strategy associated with the service transition (Gebauer and Friedli, 2005; Fliess and Lexutt, 2019; Jovanovic *et al.*, 2019; Queiroz *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, companies should pay attention to passionate employees and provide them with the necessary resources so they can develop innovative service offerings (Palo *et al.*, 2019) and introduce new professional knowledge aligned with new cultural orientation (Xing and Liu, 2016; Opazo-Basáez *et al.*, 2019).

Employees are the ones that implement the strategy of the firm so, service oriented HRM practices should reflect firm’s HRM policies when recruiting, training, empowering, compensating and rewarding employees (Homburg *et al.*, 2003; Dang *et al.*, 2019). Consequently, to have people with the appropriate profile and capabilities, HRM plays a critical role in manufacturers in service transition (Johnstone *et al.*, 2014).

Taking into consideration that the skills that are necessary for service employees are related to flexibility, increased customer-seller interaction, building relationships with customers, empathy, technical adeptness and customer-oriented “soft” skills (Baines and Lightfoot, 2013; Gebauer and Kowalkowski, 2012; Johnstone *et al.*, 2014; Dang *et al.*, 2019) the profile requirements of the employees are increased in firms that are servitizing (Fliess and Lexutt, 2019).

Training and empowering the personnel of a servitized firm contributes to a successful implementation of the strategy (Johnstone *et al.*, 2014). The changes involved when there is a service infusion in a firm could affect roles, positions and hierarchy of employees (Mathieu, 2001) and thus, could create insecurity and resistance towards changes (Antioco *et al.*, 2008). With the aim of reducing these difficulties, information sharing, cooperation, integration of departments and teamwork, and elaborating procedures could help make this transition softer (Gebauer and Fleisch, 2010).

Adapting the compensating and rewarding system also could foster the transition toward services (Neu and Brown, 2005). Indeed, rewarding service orientation, measured by service-related performance criteria, could motivate employees towards the service transition (Gebauer *et al.*, 2010a; Paiola *et al.*, 2012; Fliess and Lexutt, 2019). Particularly sales employees are very affected by the transition to services since they must change from selling large volumes of

tangible products to low order value intangible services. In this case, focusing on rewarding depending on behavior and processes, and not only on sales could contribute to align the sales employees with the service strategy of the firm (Ulaga and Loveland, 2014).

Nevertheless, in service infusion processes is not enough for single individuals to change their practices of service development or sales and delivery. Change should be collective so that the entire service and sales departments and the organization but also its customers must engage in collective changes (Fliess and Lexutt, 2019; Palo *et al.* 2019).

(Insert Table 1 here)

3. Methodology

This article reports on an in-depth and exploratory case study confirming Woodside and Wilson (2003) and it aims to achieve a deep understanding of a multi-participant process. Case studies are recommended for investigations that aim to provide conceptual contributions (Eisenhardt, 1989; Yin, 2003). The case study method allows the research of a phenomenon within a real contemporaneous context through an in-depth analysis of one or more objects, thus allowing for the gathering of broad and detailed knowledge of the studied phenomenon (Yin, 2003). One of the advantages of the method is that it allows a deep research enquiry and comes as close as possible to the research phenomena. In contrast, a single case approach limits the generalization of results and may suffer from biases from researchers and the company's employees involved (Voss *et al.*, 2002).

3.1. Case selection

The empirical evidence comes from ORBEA S.Coop. (Orbea, onwards), a manufacturing company that designs and manufactures high-value bicycles with a track record of successfully providing a product-related customization service. The company's transformation journey towards a service-oriented organization started in 2013 when it adopted an innovative strategy which focused on the end-users. Orbea adopts customization as a business model and, thus, its name will be linked to the concept of customization in the future ahead. Since then, Orbea has made significant progress, and from being a traditional bicycle manufacturer following a B2B model based on transactional processes, it is now at a relatively advanced stage of servitization in view of the success the customized bikes have had among riders. The company's commitment to being closer to the market, as a source of value creation for its end customers led it to shut down its manufacturing plant in China in 2015.

MyO is the online platform through which Orbea offers users of road, mountain, triathlon, and electric bicycles its customization service. Through this unique platform the company can offer customers a wide range of components to be assembled in more than 10 models of bicycles; after designing the physical frame, riders go for "the final touch", choosing from more than twenty different colors for the forks, frame, and Orbea logo. The wide range of combinations makes it impossible that two users could buy the same bicycle. This customization strategy has gone beyond the offer of exclusive designs and color combinations, configurations, and assemblies to meet end-user's needs. The company reinvents customization as a way of interpreting the business and triggers a transformation process that takes the company from a goods- to service-oriented organization.

In 2020, Orbea operated globally being one of the few bicycle competitors with a manufacturing plant in Europe and over 60% of its revenue comes from the sales of customized bicycles. In 2015 the company had a turnover of around 70 million euros and ended 2020 with a turnover

of more than 200 million and a workforce of more than 700 people doubling its size in the last five years and it is service-growth oriented. Therefore, the rationale for studying Orbea was thus: i) the firm has an outstanding position in the market; ii) it is focusing on the service market with customized service and solutions, and iii) access to key respondents was possible.

3.2. Data collection protocol

The research was conducted between January 2020 and August 2020. In total, 14 semi-structured, one-to-two hours long interviews regarding the role of internal elements on the move toward a service orientation took place. Respondents were highly knowledgeable informants from different departments and hierarchical levels. Table 2 provides the background information on these interviews. Different researchers participated during the interviews which contributed to data triangulation and refinement aiming to reach a certain degree of internal validity (Denzin, 2006). A case study protocol was used and a case study database with all available interview transcripts, case study write-ups, and other documents was put together to increase reliability. Complementary data were based on the researchers' observations and documents collected during the research process. We also took advantage of the experience of two of the authors who had collaborated with the company for more than twelve years with research and teaching purposes. All this information was used to triangulate findings (Gibbert and Ruigrok, 2008).

3.3. Data analysis

The information gathering and analysis process was highly iterative in nature, matched theory and reality, and followed the systematic combining logic described in Dubois and Gadde (2002) who labelled this process "abductive" and it can be characterized as going back and forth between the data and the theory, creating fruitful cross-fertilization (Oliveira *et al.* 2018; Kindström and Kowalskowski, 2014; Kowalkowski *et al.*, 2013).

Primary and secondary data was grouped into similar themes based on the research constructs and theoretical framework. To minimize bias, the researchers involved in this study selected quotes to support their research insights. The validity was enhanced by the presentation of the conclusions to the interviewees. Small adjustments were requested in this stage (Gibbert and Ruigrok, 2008; Miles and Huberman, 2004).

3.4. Measures of the research constructs

3.4.1. Service orientation of corporate culture

The service orientation of corporate culture involves two constructs: the company's corporate values and employees' behavior (Gebauer *et al.*, 2010b). These constructs refer to the value of services within manufacturing companies and the extent to which the behavior of employees is service-oriented. Considering them, we assessed the orientation of corporate values using four items that measure the value given to services by managers and employees (Gebauer *et al.*, 2010b). The value of services includes financial, strategic, and marketing opportunities (Oliva and Kallenberg, 2003; Zhang *et al.* 2020) and overall, the consideration of services as the main part of value creation is also used.

The constructs for the service orientation of employee's behavior are operationalized by using four items that refer to the different aspects of the role they have and their understanding of this role. As claimed by Neu and Brown (2005), for service businesses to expand successfully,

employees must behave as reliable troubleshooters, performance enablers, trusted advisers and enable outstanding customer performance.

3.4.2. Service orientation of HRM

On the other hand, the service orientation of HRM reflects three constructs: personnel recruitment, personnel training, and personnel assessment and compensation (Homburg *et al.*, 2003).

(Insert Table 2 here)

4. Findings

This section presents a brief description of the corporate culture and human resource management practices that play a role in the journey towards a service orientation of an organization that emerges from the case's analysis.

4.1. Service orientation of corporate culture

When questioned about the potential of services and patterns of behavior that would prove the understanding of services as the main part of the value creation of the company, the general manager explains the customization strategy not as something new but as a come-back to the historical roots of the company when they customized high value pistols and guns through the damascene technique. The renewed customization strategy, which started in 2013, has proved valuable during the last seven years, including the last one stricken by the pandemic.

4.1.1. Corporate values of the company

Managers and employees share a vision which has proven to be a powerful tool to move the whole organization in the same direction and to provide coherence to the decision processes at different levels. A new vision was formulated in 2013 with the aim of reaching a new strategic position in the very competitive bike industry and all the interviewees know what the company's vision is and everyone without exception, from the senior managers to the workers in the factory, can recognize the value of customization for the company's results in the long run and its impact on a day-to-day basis.

[...] Since 2013, the customization service has been a strategic orientation. We want to be world leaders in terms of customization, as well as the easiest brand to work with and offer a product with high added value. Those are the three pillars of our vision, and we must be consistent with it. And so, customization has emerged as a way of interpreting the business". (CEO, 2020-02-12).

[...] Orbea wants to be a leader in customized bicycles. We are taught that quality is more important than quantity. On the assembly line we have different quality control points... Orbea means quality and customization. Customization is (re)born from a strategy based on our own identity and reality" (Assembly line employee, 2020-02-26).

The analysis of the findings suggests that there is a service climate and a culture that fosters flexibility, relational markets, and customer co-production which changes the firm's atmosphere overall. This is true not only in the customer service department but also in the production departments such as painting or the assembly line. In the interviews, several employees talked about the need for flexibility in their jobs. Though, most of them share the values and behave accordingly, trying to make their contribution to offer the best service to the customers, not

everybody cares about it and the company faces a challenge with new generations that are entering the company.

Hierarchy softens and teams arise as the protagonists of this service culture, and, internally, they take advantage of new digital tools to make possible the customization strategy.

[...] "There is a lot of cross-departmental work. Hierarchy has changed: now we work in teams, it's all about teamwork. Everything is open and flexible. The challenge is to share, we use a lot (google)drive, we work on the same files, I hardly send emails with attachments" (Customer Service Manager, 2020-2-19).

4.1.2. Employee's behavior

Service culture is shared among the organization thanks to the example of the management team and a conscious practice of open communication. Moreover, according to our findings, management behavior seems to be critical to initiate service orientation at the employee's level.

[...] In a given year, the General Manager and I meet the entire staff in groups of 6 to seven people to explain the strategy and to listen to their concerns and doubts (President, 2020-2-19).

[...] The general manager is down to earth and humble. He goes to events [sports races], cooks for others, fixes bike punctures, and gives an example to the entire organization... if he does it, everyone must be humble enough to do anything and nobody is above anyone; the atmosphere is a good one. This way you can discuss work and whatever." (Sales Manager, 2020-02-26).

The concerns of the customers are of high importance in the company. True service orientation implies that the company has to provide the customers with value through those services. And customization is key in this effort. The fact that the market is increasingly demanding makes it imperative to be continually aware of what is happening and employees, each in their own area, must be very attentive not only to all the changes in customers but also to the general market needs. Indeed, employees take on the role of trusted advisers for customers and they are the ones that make an outstanding customer experience possible. In fact, of the 12 people interviewed in the firm, 10 are regular cyclists and because there is no separation between work and hobby, everyone has a deep understanding of the end-user. This can offer an insight into how important the concerns of users are to the employees.

[...] "At Orbea there are a lot of people who are passionate about the bike and the work. It's very important. There are a lot of people who turn their work into their passion and apply their passion to their work. People go out cycling on the weekend, and whether you're working one way or another, people are reading about cycling, watching cycling races, riding bikes, because they like it. It adds up and helps us all to be very connected" (Sales manager, 2020-2-6).

[...] New bikes are created in close contact with the market, and in even closer contact with the user; that is to say, it is a very, very passionate product and you have to speak the same language as users, which is basic in this industry. You must attend races, see what it takes, and there must be a constant flow of information, not only internal but also external communication: magazine reviews, chats in forums, conversations in races... I'm going to race my bike and see what the trend may be two or three years from now" (Product Manager, 2020-02-26).

Employees consider what is happening daily very important and in this way, they think they can face the problems in better conditions. They want to act as reliable trouble shooters so weekly meetings are held in each department (and in some cases, more than one).

[...] "We hold two meetings per week. In one of them, with all the team leaders, to analyse deviations and how they could affect our work in the next 3 months. If it is very important, we talk to the general manager, but if not, we decide ourselves and in half an hour everything is fixed ...

The second meeting is about customer service, we analyse the orders that have been delayed more than 5 days; all of us are aware of the importance to solve each problem... these meetings are very participative...in an hour and a half, we are done with our homework” (Logistics Manager, 2020-2-19).

Understanding the user is of the utmost importance because the product is very passionate, and this world was once far from fashions; and numerous efforts have been made in this direction, listening to the market not in the short run, but in the long one because the life cycle of a bike is 4 years. Furthermore, employees are aware that giving a good service to the customers is not only upon the company. Retailers are very important in this play, and so, the company has designed a specific platform to help them offer a good service, and they have designed an internal protocol for each of the situations that can happen in the relation with the shops. They are aware of the importance of enabling outstanding customer performance first, at the retail level and second, at the end-users level.

[...] Orbea tries to go a step further, it tries to understand the retailer by being a brand that helps sell to the retailer: sell in and sell out. How do we approach this within the business model? The retailer has to realize that with Orbea he will be more profitable and to the extent that he gets involved with a brand like Orbea, his business will do well and he will make money. (Sales manager, 2020-2-6).

[...] “This is like a love triangle. We know that we have to convince the retailer to offer a good service. We cannot do anything with a customer bypassing the retailer that sold her or him the bike... We have developed KIDE (partner in Basque language), a B2B platform, to help the retailers in their work with customers and to focus on giving them solutions... We have designed a template for the emails with more than 100 answers to respond to the most common doubts and questions that arise when we work with retailers... We have automatized the CRM to know if, after selling the bike, it has been specifically configured; if the customer has attended an event... everything to help the retailers” (Customer Service Manager, 2020-2-19).

4.2. Service orientation of human resource management

HRM is having a key role in the process of service infusion in the company.

4.2.1. Service orientation of personnel recruitment

As per recruiting, the company values not only aspects related to the technical knowledge of the candidates but also those related to their capacity to adapt to a culture of service and cooperation. Over time, selection processes have become more demanding in Orbea since customization requires hiring workers with new, more qualified, and versatile profiles which can add value.

[...] In the design area, we had nobody ten years ago; nowadays we have more than ten industrial and graphic designers. While industrial designers are fully dedicated to the development of new products, graphic design is also very important for the customization of the bikes. The incorporation of the right people has put us on the right path” (Logistics manager, 2020-02-29).

Given that customization requires more interaction and that different employees work together, the company looks for people with good teamwork skills. Hiring key individuals brings about important changes in the organization for it to be able to transform into a service focused organization. Five years ago, key organizational changes took place. The first one was hiring a new sales manager, and that decision has proven to be crucial to the transformation process of the company. Apart from recruiting from outside, there were some employees moved from one position to another (from innovation manager to operations; and from product manager to new director of product development). These recruitments and adjustments highlight that the firm is ready to change roles, positions and hierarchy of employees, in order to better implement the

customization strategy. In addition to that in 2008 there were three employees working in the marketing department whereas in 2020 there were 35 workers.

4.2.2. Service orientation of personnel training

Training that prepares versatile employees is especially important, i.e., workers who can carry out different activities depending on what is required, and who are flexible and able to adapt quickly to new situations. But there are also employees that need to be retrained, for example, the staff in the sales area who are in close contact with retailers since the online channel is expected to grow along with the use of the MyO platform. In addition to that, information sharing cooperation and teamwork is a daily practice.

[...]A lot of communication between areas and many work teams. It is a very good organization in terms of flexibility, transversality. Here, everybody talks to everybody (Area Sales, 26-2-2020).

It is also observed that the human group within Orbea, devote a lot of dedication, hard work, passion and an ambition to keep improving and to grow.

4.2.3. Service orientation of personnel assessment and compensation

Since 2017, the CEO along with the director of people management have been working on the design of a new compensation system in which customization is considered a key aspect. As per compensation and promotion, the CEO explains why a former product manager was promoted to the position of product development director.

[...] His mental structure matches what we were seeking for that position... someone who takes his time to develop excellent products. He did not mind making reiterations about something that he did not find satisfactory enough. It was something that I wanted to install into the whole organization, and his promotion is a way of declaring to the organization what we want to achieve" (CEO, 2020-02-12).

The sales area is particularly affected by the transition towards services. Therefore, a special effort was made to strengthen this area recruiting a new Sales Director, new sales personnel and thus, transforming the commercial structure and the front office. In addition to that, the fact that Orbea is cooperative means that turnover of highly talented employees is lower than in other types of organizations, since workers are also owners. And so, the stability, commitment and passion of the human group that makes up the company means that decision making with an "owner" and long-term approach that favors a focus on the customer and service. We observed that what we can call "emotional salary" is very relevant for the employees (the feeling of purpose, passion for the product, autonomy or belonging, are elements that increase commitment towards the firm). Eventually, we observe that the change towards services is a collective transformation that is present in all departments and functions all over the organization.

5. Discussion

5.1. Service orientation of corporate culture

In order to answer our first research question we have looked at the corporate values and employee's behavior (Homburg *et al.*, 2003; Gebauer *et al.* 2010b; Pereira *et al.*, 2018; Fliess and Lexutt, 2019; Dang *et al.*, 2019; Jovanovic *et al.*, 2019), when applying a customization strategy (Sousa and Da Silveira, 2019; Ullah and Narain, 2020).

5.1.2. Corporate values of the company

Establishing the strategic orientation is the first and most important step in a change process (Gebauer and Fleisch, 2010; Fliess and Lexutt, 2019; Queiroz *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, this should be accompanied by a shared vision which in the case under study has proven to be a powerful tool to move the entire organization towards a customization structure and environment (Bowen *et al.*, 1989), where flexibility, relational marketing and customer orientation is promoted and recognized (Bowen and Schneider, 2014).

When interviewees explain their competitive advantage against the companies that only design in house and manufacture in Asia, they explicitly recognize that customization is of a strategic importance validating the findings of Gebauer *et al.* (2010b) about services being considered the main part of value creation. In this vein, they are fully aware that the shift towards services through the customization strategy has been beneficial to gain more customers, to keep them happier, and to increase their loyalty confirming its financial, strategic and marketing positive impact (Oliva and Kallenberg, 2003; Oliveira *et al.* 2018; Zhang *et al.* 2020).

Culture seems to play a distinct role in the introduction of a service logic into Orbea and appears to be an umbrella element for the entire organization (Grönroos and Halle, 2010). The company has a culture based on the love for bicycles which is spread throughout the company. The interviewees have described a service climate (Ostrom *et al.*, 2010) when considering the potential that services have for the company.

Infusing services through customization increases the interaction of the company with retailers and end-users putting the company at a relatively advanced stage of servitization (Martinez *et al.*, 2010; Sousa and Da Silveira, 2019). This interaction enables the company to get access to key information on the latest market demands, unique needs, usage of the product and therefore, the company can better respond to its customers with new services including result-oriented ones in a near future (Sousa and Da Silveira, 2019).

5.1.2 Employee's behavior

Management behavior is critical to initiate a service orientation at employees level. All of the interviewees share the concerns of the customers but the staff in the front office (Marketing, Product Managers, Sales and Customer Care) is the one who plays the role of mediator between the organization and customers (Oliveira *et al.*, 2018), listening to them and translating their needs and problems to those in the back-office (Purchase and Manufacturing). This arises the question of the match/mismatch between strategy-organizational design of the company (Gebauer *et al.*, 2010b; Gebauer and Kowalkowski, 2012). Though, in our research, we have found two reasons to mitigate the effects in the latter of not being in the frontline: first is that they have taken advantage of collaborative work (multiple reunions and digital tools) that "break the silos" and allows to avoid the isolation of service professionals (Pereira *et al.* 2018), and second, this "translation" is easier to understand because most of the workers in the company (as declared by the interviewees) are bike enthusiasts and they regularly interact with customers and other cyclists during their free time (weekends, holidays, amateur contests, or the events sponsored by the company).

5.2. Service orientation of human resource management

To answer the second research question we have looked at HRM policies regarding recruitment, training, and compensation also contribute to aligning employees with a common project and a particular direction (Gebauer *et al.*, 2010b; Zhang and Banerji, 2017; Fliess and Lexutt, 2019; Queiroz *et al.* 2020). We have looked at the following elements.

5.2.1. Service orientation of personnel recruitment

Recruiting new personnel and promoting the right people to key positions appears to be one of the decisions that have been well taken (Gebauer *et al.*, 2010b). The growth in sales of over 30% per year at Orbea in the last three years has been accompanied by many new recruitments in several departments, to reinforce the relational skills necessary for a culture of service (Baines and Lightfoot, 2013; Gebauer and Kowalkowski, 2012; Johnstone *et al.*, 2014; Dang *et al.*, 2019). In addition to increasing the sensitivity towards the external retailers and customers, a relevant finding is that these new capabilities also make it possible to improve the internal relationship between departments, breaking down the traditional silos between them.

The new and more demanding profile in a servitized organization requires employees with technical skills but also soft, relational and teamwork skills, to deal with more frequent interactions outside, but also, inside the organization. Accordingly, new recruitments and the adjustments in positions, highlight that the firm is ready to change roles, positions and hierarchy of employees, in order to better implement the customization strategy.

5.2.2. Service orientation of personnel training

Previous literature (Jovanovic *et al.*, 2019; Ulaga and Loveland, 2014) has stressed the importance of recruiting new employees for sales, customer service and marketing departments, and thus, the former employees of these departments should be trained. Moreover, our findings show that in a customization process all workers require a service approach, and consequently, they must acquire new skills that reduces insecurities and resistances (Antioco *et al.* 2008) and could make this transition softer through cooperation, information sharing and teamwork among different departments (Gebauer and Fleisch, 2010). All this would introduce new professional knowledge aligned with new service orientation (Xing and Liu, 2016; Opazo-Basález *et al.*, 2019) and would increase the internal cohesion of the organization.

5.2.3. Service orientation of personnel assessment and compensation

With the aim of aligning with the customization strategy, personnel assessment and compensation should consider service-related aspects and not only sales (Ulaga and Loveland, 2014). Rewarding depending on behavior and processes could contribute to align sales employees with service strategy. In addition to that we observe that apart from the monetary salary, the importance of emotional salary (proud to work in the firm, autonomy, passion for the product, the feeling of purpose) is also very relevant for the employees. Therefore, the whole organization should adapt the assessment and compensation systems in a customization strategy and should try to maintain the elements of the emotional salary. All these systems should take into consideration the collective nature needed for a customization strategy (Palo *et al.* 2019), and thus, this should be integrated in the assessment and compensation system of the employees of the whole organization.

6. Conclusion

Based on a case study, three significant contributions are made. First, it contributes to the existing knowledge on the role of internal elements for introducing a service logic into an organization and a validation of the constructs for measuring service orientation of corporate culture and human resource management policies identified in the literature is made.

Second, our research contributes by identifying three new internal elements affecting the service infusion in a customization strategy process regarding the service orientation of corporate culture: i) a shared vision towards services is fundamental to move the entire organization if it is built among all the members of the organization and it is lived out in every day of their work (and this case, of their life because nearly all of them are bike runners); ii) rooting the service orientation in the past history and results of the company helps very much to internalize this new shift towards services; iii) service orientation is implemented and fed back by passion and enthusiastic joint work among all the departments of the company and the regular use of collaborative tools. Moreover, two new elements are identified regarding HRM. On the one hand, the importance of the emotional salary among workers of the organization. And, on the other hand, that the service orientation of human resource management should be deployed in the whole organization so the service infusion is understood and shared by all workers in a collective way.

Third, the study highlights some managerial implications: i) top managers have to invest time and resources to create a shared vision that will guide the whole organization to the strategic goal; ii) these top managers (i.e. President and General Manager) must involve directly in the shift towards services becoming real service evangelists, giving direct examples of what it really means, imply in the challenge and behave accordingly; iii) new service orientation is better understood when it is properly explained and change is rooted in past history of the company; iv) service orientation demands new relational skills and new tools to foster collaborative work; that, by the way help reinforcing the share vision among all the teams in the organization; v) efforts must be rewarded, and emotional salary plays a distinctive and positive role to strengthen the willingness of the staff to embrace this shift from a goods- to a service-focused organization; vi) financial positive results play a very important role to convince the whole company that they have to move towards this new mindset. So maybe, every step taken must be focused to obtain some short-term positive success.

This study presents limitations. Although triangulation techniques were employed to increase data robustness, data collected from interviews can suffer from personal bias. In addition, findings are limited to a single research case undertaken in a cooperative company. Then, there is no space for generalizations.

Several opportunities for future research can be identified. Firstly, as conclusions are based on a manufacturing company with a customization strategy, researchers could arrange a benchmark analysis comparing this case with different sectors and/or different service strategies to discover if corporate service culture and human resources management practices are similar or different. Secondly, the association between customization strategies and performance indicators could be also analyzed in manufacturing companies. Thirdly, as mentioned, our case is a cooperative so, another line of research could be to study whether a different type of ownership has an impact on the corporate culture and in human resource management. Finally, how structure changes in a customization strategy could be further research.

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